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MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *The article discusses the issue of a new form and method of teaching, a new approach to the learning process. The main goal that I set for myself by applying modern technologies in teaching a foreign language is to show how technologies can be effectively used to improve the quality of foreign language teaching for students, the formation and development of their communicative culture, and teaching practical foreign language acquisition.*

Keywords: *method, communicative culture, self-organization, self-development, flexibility, critical thinking.*

In recent years, the issue of the use of modern technologies in the educational process has been increasingly raised. My task as a teacher is to create conditions for practical language acquisition for each student, to choose teaching methods that would allow each student to show their activity, creativity, and cognitive activity in the process of learning a foreign language.

The use of modern tools such as computer programs and Internet technologies, as well as collaborative learning and project methods allow us to solve these problems. Active learning is based on the fact that the learner is increasingly faced with the need to solve problematic situations in real life. This method is aimed at self-organization and self-development of the personality. The basic principle is that the learner himself is the creator of his knowledge.

Active learning is, of course, a priority at the present stage of teaching a foreign language. It is necessary to give preference to active teaching methods that are aimed at developing students' independence, flexibility, and critical thinking. The object of the study is foreign language speech activity as the most important means of intercultural interaction in general. Intercultural interaction is possible only if students have formed all the components of foreign language communicative competence (IQ): educational, linguistic, speech, socio-cultural and compensatory.

The modern approach to teaching is to build it on a technological basis. The general principles and rules of teaching technology are as follows: setting goals; turning the student's activity into his independent activity; specifying educational and developmental goals and methods; thematic planning, including a brief description of the final results and building the entire chain of individual classes connected by one logic; control at each stage of the student's educational and cognitive activity; stimulating his creative activity, focusing on the student who is not only knowledgeable, but also able; a variety of forms and methods of teaching, preventing the universalization of a particular medium or form.

An important factor for the selection of methods is the principle of continuity of different levels of education, ensuring the continuity of education. The optimal way to form a foreign language communicative competence and ensure the continuity of secondary vocational education is to integrate into the traditional educational process such modern methods of teaching foreign languages as learning in collaboration, using the Internet and multimedia. Innovative technologies in education are, first of all, information and communication technologies, which are inextricably linked with the use of computerized learning. The introduction of information and communication technologies into the learning process began not so long ago. However, the rate of its spread is incredibly rapid. The use of Internet technologies in foreign language classes is an effective factor for developing students' motivation. In most cases, students enjoy working with a computer. Since classes are held in an informal setting, students are given freedom of action, and some of them can "show off" their knowledge in the field of ICT. The prospects for using Internet technologies today are quite wide.

This may be: Correspondence with residents of the countries of the languages being studied by e-mail;

Participation in international Internet conferences, seminars and other network projects of this kind; Creation and posting of websites and presentations online (They can be created jointly with the teacher and the student. In addition, presentations can be exchanged between teachers from different countries). As pedagogical experience shows, the work on creating online resources is interesting to students for its novelty, relevance, and creativity. The organization of cognitive activity of students in small groups provides an opportunity for each student to be active. The worldwide network provides a unique opportunity for foreign language learners to use authentic texts, communicate with native speakers, create a natural language environment and develop the ability for intercultural interaction.

The purposeful use of Internet materials in foreign language classes makes it possible to effectively solve a number of didactic tasks, namely, to improve reading skills.; replenish vocabulary with vocabulary of a modern foreign language; improve the skills of monologue and dialogical utterance by discussing online materials; to form a stable motivation for foreign language activities in the process of discussing issues of interest to everyone. The Internet provides exceptional opportunities in the process of learning a foreign language for mastering the means of communication in writing, providing an opportunity to implement a communicative approach to teaching written types of speech activity. For the purpose of teaching a foreign language, both free online communication and e-mail communication are used. To achieve maximum effect, it is necessary to use a wide range of innovative, including, of course, a variety of media educational technologies in the learning process. In modern methodology, multimedia is considered as one of the many technical means of teaching, which is capable of solving a range of tasks determined by the didactic properties and functions of this software. From this point of view, multimedia is a technical means of teaching that integrates different types of information – audio, visual, and provides interactive interaction with the learner. The properties of interactivity, i.e. The ability to control the process of presenting information involves the learner in an active learning process, stimulates his cognitive activity, and helps maintain a stable motivation for learning.

This learning tool (multimedia) allows you to:

- integrate different types of information in a single container object (text, sound, video) and present it by influencing different human senses;
- develop skills of working with large amounts of information of various types;
- develop critical thinking;
- stimulate the cognitive process;
- interactively interact with trainees;
- adapt to the requests of the latter;
- organize group work in multimedia environments;
- to form a stable motivation for learning;
- to create conditions as close to reality as possible for the development of educational and professional skills.

Multimedia, as a teaching tool, differs from other teaching tools primarily in two main didactic properties: an integrative approach to presenting information in various forms (text, sound, video, etc.) and interactive interaction with the learner, which make it possible to solve many modern didactic tasks, namely, to form key competencies identified by regulatory documents. as the basis of the content of modern education:

1. Competence in the field of independent cognitive activity;
2. Competence in the field of civil and social activities;
3. Competence in the field of social and labor activity;
4. Competence in the household sphere;
5. Competence in the field of cultural and leisure activities.

Modern computer tools allow you to create new computer programs, both educational, training, and monitoring. These kinds of programs are created for special educational purposes and are widely used in the process of independent and homework when learning a foreign language. When working through the material on your own, using a computer ensures:

- 1) Free operation mode
- 2) Unlimited working time
- 3) exclusion of subjective factors
- 4) maximum support in learning a foreign language.

Computer controls increase the efficiency of independent work, efficiency in obtaining results, and increase the objectivity of the assessment by 20-25%.

The introduction of modern methods and techniques into the educational process makes it possible to realize learning goals based on new approaches to education:

1. To strengthen the practical orientation of education, focusing on the development of personal qualities capable of effective life in a rapidly changing world;
2. Ensure continuity of general and vocational education;
3. By ensuring a functional command of a foreign language, encourage the student to continue language education;
4. To develop students' independent work skills and awareness of the need for continuous education and self-improvement;
5. Strengthen the individualization and differentiation of the learning process of foreign languages based on the personal experience of the student;
6. To promote the professional growth of teachers and the creation of a community of creative teachers.

The use of innovative foreign language teaching technologies in our academy is based on the development of subject-subject relations between the teacher and the students. These relations presuppose: recognition of the student as the main value of the educational process; transition to cooperation (the teacher acts as the organizer of educational activities in which the student conducts an independent search for knowledge); identification and maximum use of the student's subjective experience, coordination of his experience with socially significant experience; activation of the student's personal functions. The choice of technology by each particular teacher is based on an analysis of the pedagogical situation. The definition of the technology of teaching a foreign language will necessarily be influenced, for example, by the amount of time allocated to an academic subject, a separate topic; the level of preparation of students, their age characteristics; the material equipment of the educational institution; the level of preparation of the teacher himself.

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